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XR2INDUSTRY platform overview

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1 Introduction

This document will present the overall structure of the XR2INDUSTRY platform, combining the strategic European Lynx headsets with an extensive software architecture to enable the deployment and usage of XR solutions at scale in different industries and job contexts.

Each of the subsystems of our platform is presented in some more detail, together with relevant standards and APIs that will be considered to support interactions between them (internal to XR2INDUSTRY platform instances) and towards external systems that may be present in industrial environments.

Following this introduction, the contributions of the project's software technology partners are described and how they related to the overall platform architecture and responsibilities.

2 Platform overview

The XR2INDUSTRY software architecture must support the project goals of interoperability, standardization, and scalability for mass adoption of XR technologies in different industries.

Besides supporting XR-related features, the platform must also be ready for integration in existing digital environments and work processes.

The schema below illustrates the 6 major subsystems that will define the platform in a modular and open architecture.

XR solutions commonly target the following related subsystems:

- XR devices of different types that are needed to provide the XR-enriched experiences to the end-users.
- Content management of the required applications, 3D assets and other related media.
- Device management solutions to efficiently configure large fleets of XR devices.

These core XR-related subsystems are also part of the XR2INDUSTRY platform but in addition we define “gateways” to the industrial working context and its digital environment:

- Activity management to associate XR experiences with concrete tasks/activities that are typically already managed in operational/workforce management systems.

- Identity management as the basis to support security, privacy, data governance etc.
- Context management as a bridge to the operational environment in which professional activities must be performed. E.g. to collect real-time data from IoT devices, environmental hazards/conditions, personal preferences/skills etc. In short, any contextual information that may be used to support personalised, adaptive, optimised XR experiences in a professional context.

This architecture should enable the introduction of XR solutions in different manners:

- As a standalone platform, providing all needed features for pilots without requiring big integration efforts upfront. I.e. Activity, Identity and Context Management must be possible without dependencies on external systems.
- As a “plugin” on existing digitalized work environments for applying XR at scale while minimizing impact on existing operational processes and tools for most stakeholders. I.e. Activity, Identity and Context Management must be able to act as intermediaries towards external systems.

Below we will describe the goals and responsibilities of each subsystem in some more detail, together with their interactions with the other subsystems and API's towards external platforms.

2.1 XR device

XR2INDUSTRY focuses on having a true and advanced European XR headset: Lynx. Its device design and production are managed in WP2. Here we describe the main interactions and features by Lynx for creating and enabling XR apps and experiences.

2.1.1 XR device interactions

The XR device is at the center of an XR solution. It is the wearable device that can deliver rich immersive user experiences, in our case for learning and performing professional tasks in different industries.

To deliver effective learning and support experiences, the device must be integrated in a larger ecosystem where we can differentiate two major types of interactions:

- Locally on the device:
 - XR apps depend on core XR-related features on the device they're running on, potentially also on some optional advanced features.
 - They will have dependencies on device SDKs, and/or presence of other apps/services on the same device, that can provide the required features.
- Remotely with (cloud-based) software platforms:
 - XR devices must be manageable (remotely) via a Device Management solution.
 - Devices and users must be identifiable via an Identity Management system.
 - XR content must be downloaded and safely stored on the device, from the Content Management system.

2.1.2 Lynx core features

The Lynx headsets are fully compliant with the OpenXR standard.

They are Android devices supporting both VR and MR use cases, the latter is implemented in a so-called “Pass through” mode of the headset.

User interactions are supported by gesture recognition or controllers.

Lynx devices support remote device management by Android MDM solutions to register a device, configure it, install & update applications and execute commands such as starting/stopping an application etc.

2.2 Identity and access management

Identity and Access Management (IAM) is a crucial domain in XR2INDUSTRY, as well for human actors as for physical devices and objects as for digital assets.

Within XR2INDUSTRY we will apply following main approaches for IAM :

- Human actors :
 - Platform access accounts will be managed in a **Keycloak**¹ instance. They will be associated with a person's Decentralized Identifier (**DID**²).
- Physical assets (XR devices & other devices/objects):
 - We assume that any device that needs access to XR2INDUSTRY in an autonomous fashion (i.e. without a human user) will have a unique and persistent Device ID combined with a digital certificate.
 - We will also look at using DIDs for devices directly owned/managed via XR2INDUSTRY.
 - XR apps will need to be able to obtain the Device ID and DID through a Device SDK, so they can use it in their requests to XR2INDUSTRY backend services.
- Digital assets (apps, 3D models etc):
 - When registered in the XR2INDUSTRY Content Repository, they will get:
 - a DID for when the asset needs to be identified as part of an access/trust process.
 - a simple Asset UUID with which the asset and its metadata can be addressed/found in a repository.

Access to XR2INDUSTRY applications and services will be secured according to OpenID Connect³ (OIDC) and the underlying OAuth 2.0⁴ standards.

As DID is still a recent practice and true decentralization incurs a significant extra infrastructural burden, W3C has launched a lightweight method to allow bootstrapping the application of DIDs: DID web⁵. XR2INDUSTRY will start with this DID method and our IAM will act as target system to resolve the DID in the host's web domain.

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>

³ <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works/>

⁴ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6749>

⁵ <https://w3c-ccg.github.io/did-method-web/>

2.2.1 IAM Interactions

Human actors accessing an XR2INDUSTRY subsystem will always need to be authenticated.

There is only one exception : during demonstration sessions of XR applications on *trusted* XR devices someone must be able to quickly experience a trial XR experience without needing to register & authenticate as a user him/herself. This is a mode supported by the current Passerelle XR AMP, where the XR device is assumed to be under the control of a trusted person for a risk-less and time-constrained demonstration activity.

XR2INDUSTRY APIs exposed to external systems and third-party (XR) applications will be secured via OAUTH 2.0.

XR2INDUSTRY frontends (web and native apps) will be based on OIDC for authentication. We will investigate how to integrate OIDC for Verifiable Credentials, following up on the progress of:

- [Digital Credentials Protocols Working Group](#) at the OpenID Foundation
- [Keycloak roadmap for OIDC VC integration](#)

2.2.2 IAM APIs

IAM APIs are a core requirement both for XR2INDUSTRY internal and external interactions, i.e. by actors and subsystems that are part of the platform or external to it.

We will not invent proprietary APIs for IAM, but apply and integrate the following standards:

Name	Specification type	API spec
did:web	W3C draft	DID Web method
OIDC 1.0	OIDF Specification	OIDC 1.0
OAUTH 2.0	IETF Standard	OAUTH 2.0

2.3 Activity management

Professional use of XR in different industries implies that XR technology can be embedded in existing work procedures and tools.

In a human-centric approach we focus on the Activities that someone has to perform in their work context. XR devices and applications must fit in fluently, as needed for optimal performance of someone's professional Activities.

Depending on the industry and on the domain of activities, there is a wide range of existing work methods and accompanying types of digital platforms already in use. For instance for training activities, there are Learning Management Systems (LMS's). For after-sales support there are Customer Case Management systems, Field Service Management systems etc. Enterprise Resource Planning and Manufacturing Operations Management systems rule the digital world of manufacturing.

To limit the hurdles for introducing XR-enabled solutions, it's crucial to determine the best ways for integration of the XR2INDUSTRY platform with those existing environments.

Training is a primary use case of XR technology, often provided as VR experiences but also AR/MR can be valuable in training activities.

But XR can also enrich/improve other professional activities such as remote assistance, on-the-job guidance etc. which are especially relevant for Field services to enhance a worker's collaboration and/or self-support options.

XR Activities can be supported by two main types of Applications:

- Dedicated (hard-coded) applications and content, specific for a given task and/or knowledge domain. E.g. a VR application that has fixed training scenarios and content in a virtual world to learn trainees how to connect a residential home to a public sewer system.
- Generic XR content “player” applications that can dynamically load XR content and scenario information. These can provide a multitude of XR experiences based on a library of compatible XR assets and scenarios. Often these “players” are accompanied by no-code/low-code authoring tools to create scenarios and content.

The XR2INDUSTRY Activity Management (AM) subsystem will act as the bridge between the industrial digital platforms and the XR devices and applications.

2.3.1 AM interactions

The AM system consists of following main components:

- A cloud-based AM solution with a web-based front-end and backend API's.
- An on-device XR Workplace application where the user can be welcomed in an immersive environment and can find & start the planned XR activities.
- Dedicated or generic XR applications providing the content and interactions to perform the activities as needed.

Besides providing the correct Activity (meta-)data to XR users on their devices, the AM system must also provide Coordinators and other stake-holders with the necessary features for:

- Defining a library of supported Activity types a.k.a. Activity Definitions
- Planning Activities and assigning/enrolling Participants
- Alternatively accessing work planning in external platforms and creating Activity proxy instances in AM
- Managing licensed devices to run the needed XR applications and provide the XR Activities to the participants
- Monitoring and reporting on progress and other KPIs

We can differentiate following interactions:

- AM backend may be able to provided adaptive XR support by obtaining (real-time) information from Context Management (e.g. skills & preferences, IoT sensor information, ...)
- AM backend must support registering and licensing XR devices. It will typically act as a front-end and will delegate most of the device interactions to Device Management.
- AM backend must support the XR Workplace app for:
 - Obtaining the (metadata for) the required VR Workplace
 - Retrieving planned / allowed Activities for the user

- Launching Activity performance Sessions
- XR Workplace app must be able to:
 - Identify the user
 - Launch the needed XR applications
- XR applications must be able to
 - Load any needed content from Content Management
 - Read any needed context information from Context Management
 - Send Activity performance data to the AM backend

2.3.2 AM APIs

2.3.2.1 Standard APIs

XR2INDUSTRY will support existing integration standards and APIs for our two focus application domains. These will provide following main features:

- Ability to synchronize XR activity schedules with tasks already defined and planned in an organization's existing digital environment.
- Ability to launch an XR activity from existing digital worker tools.
- Sending activity performance data to an organization's digital environment.

2.3.2.2 Training

For training activities, organizations typically use some form of Learning Management System (LMS) or Learning eXperience Platform (LXP). Traditional systems typically offer web-based content, assessments, performance monitoring etc.

Two important families of standards are relevant in modern "e-Learning" environments where we would like to integrate XR training. Three organizations have been instrumental in providing these standards.

1EdTech⁶ (previously known as IMS Global) is a global consortium focusing on promoting interoperability in educational technology with the goal of improving the digital learning experience in K-12, higher education and corporate training. Its standards typically focus on LMS-centric learning environments and how to integrate other digital tools with them.

Advanced Distributed Learning⁷ (ADL) is a U.S. Department of Defense initiative that focuses on the development and promotion of e-learning standards. While the emphasis is on military and government training, its work on enabling the delivery of learning content and analysing learning results across diverse environments is also being applied in corporate and educational environments where new educational technologies such as XR are used. Besides formal training, ADL's standards also tackle on-the-job learning, mobile learning environments and other kinds of learning experiences that may happen outside of traditional LMS environments.

IEEE Learning Technology Standards Committee⁸ (IEEE LTSC) has taken over the governance of the xAPI standard which was previously maintained by ADL. This process was part of a larger effort to ensure that xAPI, which started as a project within ADL, could gain the widespread credibility and governance needed to be adopted more broadly across various industries beyond

⁶ <https://www.1edtech.org/>

⁷ <https://adlnet.gov/>

⁸ <https://sagroups.ieee.org/ltsc/>

defense and government. IEEE is also the home of the ARLEM standard, described in the section below on Content Management.

Following standards with their APIs will be supported in XR2INDUSTRY:

Name	Source	Description	API spec
Learning Tools Interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LTI 1.3 • Deep Linking 2.0 	1Edtech	Launching external learning tools Discovering external content	LTI overview LTI spec Deep Linking spec
XAPI (IEEE 9274.1.1)	IEEE	Tracing and understanding (performance of) (learning) experiences and their outcomes across wide variety of platforms and technologies	IEEE XAPI Overview ADL XAPI 1.0.3 spec

A Learning Record Store (LRS) is a central component in a XAPI-based edtech architecture. It collects learning data/events from all kinds of learning/training tools. The stored data can be analysed for several purposes such as offering adaptive training content, feeding dashboards or providing criteria for generating (open) badges to certify an accomplishment.

When an LMS is present in the training environment, it can launch XR (and other) learning activities via LTI.

2.3.2.3 XR job guidance

ISA-95 is a well-known interoperability standard in many industrial contexts with a high adoption rate.

One part of ISA-95 is about **Work Definitions**, defining the tasks that must be performed on a level of detail relevant for Operations Management and that can be assigned/scheduled for resources (human operators and/or automations) on Level 3 in the Purdue Reference Model⁹.

Work Definitions can contain more fine-grained information on detailed steps to be performed in a sequence to perform a task. These are represented in ISA-95 **Workflow Specifications**.

These are often applied to represent Standard Operating Procedures in a digital manner, also known as Digital Work Instructions (DWI).

Since ISA-95 is a specification, an implementation of ISA-95 must be chosen to make it practically usable. A prominent ISA-95 implementation is B2MML which is an XML implementation specified using XSD files which are XML schema files. Recent versions also support JSON representations for data exchanges.

2.3.2.4 XR2INDUSTRY AM concepts

Our AM model will be based on three core concepts, common in many similar systems:

- Activity Definitions : defining what types of activities are supported with their detailed metadata.
- Activities : specifying what must be done (based on the related Activity Definitions & on

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Purdue_Enterprise_Reference_Architecture

relevant Context information), when and by whom. The “unit of work” around which everything evolves in AM.

- Sessions : an attempt by one or more participants at performing an assigned Activity. There may be several Sessions before an Activity is successfully completed.

2.4 Content management

Preparing digital content for training or for on-the-job support typically requires significant effort and budget. On the other hand, there is a lot of content available out there, but often hidden in proprietary repositories.

The lack of open and standardized content-sharing frameworks is an important barrier to distribution and reuse of XR content. Such frameworks should tackle not only technical aspects of interoperability (both for content creation as for sharing) but also governance of intellectual property and copyright protection mechanisms.

XR2INDUSTRY will provide a solution to store and share content (and apps) based on the concepts and standards for “data spaces”, which are at the core of the European strategy for data governance. These provide blueprints, core building blocks and consent/licensing solutions that we will apply to XR content management.

The most important type of content that is shared by the platform are trainings or experiences. Scenarios for AR experiences can be modeled by the standard defined by IEEE ARLEM¹⁰, including AR augmentations to be applied. These can then be shared and interpreted by different application providers. XR2INDUSTRY will also investigate how ARLEM can be applied in VR training cases.

The ARLEM standard is divided in two interdependent sub-standards: activity ML and workplace ML. You may refer to the official specification of ARLEM for more detailed information.

Figure 1: High overview of ARLEM standard.

Another standard we will apply, is ISA-95¹¹, also known as the International Society of Automation standard 95, is a global standard for enterprise-control system integration. ISA-95 facilitates clear and consistent communication between different systems within a

¹⁰ <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9368405>

¹¹ <https://www.isa.org/standards-and-publications/isa-standards/isa-standards-committees/isa95>

manufacturing environment. It is not designed from an XR or life-long learning perspective (c.f. IEEE 1589-2020). Nevertheless, it is an excellent choice as an XR training representation, especially for manufacturing related trainings where ISA-95 is already used.

2.4.1 Content Management APIs

As content management is largely based on the *data spaces* philosophy and architecture, we will not invent proprietary APIs for this mechanism. You may find the definition of the APIs and bindings for *data spaces* in the documentation of International Data Spaces¹².

The Dataspace protocol is also combined with other standards that provide other functionalities such as identification, catalogues or policy management:

Name	Specification type	API spec
did:web	W3C draft	DID Web method
DCAT	W3C Recommendation	DCATv3
ODRL	W3C Recommendation	ODRLv2.2

2.5 Device management

For small-scale XR use someone with a minimal technical understanding is able to setup and maintain a couple of XR devices by combining existing free PC-based tools with actions to be performed on each headset.

But for applying XR at scale with a large fleet of headsets, some form of dedicated and user-friendly (Mobile) Device Management (MDM) helps a lot. In recent years a couple of commercial providers have delivered such solutions, e.g. dedicated XR MDM solutions such as ArborXR¹³, ManageXR¹⁴ or existing solutions opening up to XR like (ex VMWare) Workspace One UEM¹⁵, and others. These products are not conceived in an open way, each having their own (partial) SDKs and APIs and frontends which are difficult to integrate in higher-level platforms such as XR2INDUSTRY.

With XR2INDUSTRY our ambition is to define the core features for an MDM that can be used in a modular and open way, aligned with the overall goals of the project. This will be based on the definition of APIs for the different interactions between platform subsystems.

2.5.1 MDM interactions

The MDM solution will consist of three main parts:

- A cloud-based MDM platform consisting of a web-based front-end and backend API's.
- An MDM agent application to be installed on the XR device
- A (PC) application to register an XR device for the first time ("Installer" app)

¹² <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/ids-knowledgebase/v/dataspace-protocol/>

¹³ <https://arborxr.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.managexr.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.omnissa.com/workspace-one-unified-endpoint-management/>

We can differentiate following interactions:

- MDM Cloud backend
 - MDM backend must support first-time device registration / enrollment.
 - MDM backend APIs can be used by Activity Management to ensure XR devices are setup correctly to provide the needed/planned Activity support.
 - MDM backend may need to access Content Management APIs to find and transfer the content files and application binaries that must be provisioned on the XR devices.
- MDM device agent
 - The device agent must interact with Android APIs and the Lynx SDK for:
 - Configuring the device
 - Storing files, installing applications, ...
 - Getting live device information
 - The device agent must be reachable by remote systems such as the MDM backend and the Activity Management system so they can trigger the MDM actions on the device.

2.5.2 MDM APIs

The APIs planned in XR2INDUSTRY to support the above MDM-related interactions are listed below.

Title	Short description
Register device	Provides all necessary information required to register a device in the MDM system, including identification and initial configuration data.
Query registered devices	Retrieves a list of all devices currently registered in the MDM system.
Find a particular device	Searches for a specific device based on defined criteria such as device database ID, name, or other attributes.
Get live device information	Provides real-time information about a device, including status, connectivity, and other dynamic parameters.
Query applications on device	Lists all applications installed on a specified device
Query files on device	Retrieves a list of files stored on the device including file metadata
Download file from device	
Send device command	Current list of identified commands: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set WiFi configuration • Upload File • Install Application • Start Application • Stop Application
Get scheduled device commands	Retrieves a list of scheduled commands pending execution on the device.
Configure device	This is a composite action on a device, combining a set of commands by sending a configuration dataset/script

	in a file instead of requesting a series of commands one-by-one.
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The XR2INDUSTRY platform architecture will research and demonstrate an open MDM solution based on documented APIs, for instance used by the Activity Management Platform to provide a seamless XR experience towards its end-users.

2.6 Context Management

We define **Context** as any information that can be relevant to characterize in detail the situation, environment and modalities in which someone performs an activity and interacts with the XR2INDUSTRY platform and/or applications.

When this information is available and used, XR solutions can be made **context-aware**.

Through context-awareness, the applications can support personalized, adaptive and optimized XR experiences, with rich and relevant information, both in training and in on-the-job support scenarios.

For example:

- When the XR app can identify IoT things that are nearby and can obtain live status alarms for them, a technician can be notified and be guided with the correct work instructions to resolve the specific alarm condition of that specific IoT device. Instead of the technician needing to search through lists of phenomena and of procedures to follow.
- When the XR app knows the skills level and language preferences of a user, training content can be personalized.

2.6.1 Context management elements

The elements that build up context information can for our purposes be grouped in following categories:

1. **Personal**: here we differentiate mainly between skills versus preferences.
2. **Tools (hardware & software)**: take into account their features and affordances.
3. **Parts and products**: the physical things to be used for installations and repair.
4. **Environmental**: everything in the workplace. Location, surrounding space, things, devices, weather conditions, lighting, ...

Whereas a lot of this will be the responsibility of the XR applications, XR2INDUSTRY will integrate support for a number of core context elements in the platform.

For **Personal context**, XR2INDUSTRY will focus on integration with

- European and national **skills classifications**. ESCO¹⁶ will be the principal classification.
- Industry **skills management systems** via standard APIs.

¹⁶ <https://esco.ec.europa.eu/en>

Information about **Tools, Parts** and (Environmental) **workplace** could be represented and shared in **standard ISA-95 models**.

Other Environmental elements may be accessed via IoT protocols and platforms. Due to the large variety of choices in IoT, this will be defined more specifically while working on WP5.

2.6.2 Context management standards and APIs

Related to skills classification and management we will incorporate following items

Name	Source	Description	Info/spec
ESCO	European Commission	European skills, competencies, qualifications and occupations classification	ESCO site
Open Badges	1EdTech		Open badges site
EDC	European Commission	European Digital Credential for Learning	EDC site

Related to Tools, Parts and Products, we will apply

Name	Source	Description
Equipment model	ISA-95	Representation of a workplace with the equipment present
Materials model	ISA-95	Representation of parts/materials to be used

Specification documents can be obtained from ISA-95.

XML schema's can be found on the [B2MML site](#).

3 Passerelle XR

3.1 Introduction

Supportsquare's Passerelle XR offers core features of the XR2INDUSTRY platform related to:

- Identity management
- Activity management
- Content management

To support a seamless end-user experience, it also provides device management features out-of-the-box without striving to be a complete MDM solution.

Passerelle XR consists of several pillars, all supported by a SaaS management platform including a web portal.

Passerelle Explore facilitates the exploration of a company/sector/domain in a collaborative immersive environment. Multiple participants can join and can experience an interactive virtual lobby or workplace. Simple concept presentations and training can also be integrated.

The same virtual environment can be used as reception area for VR training. After a PIN-code identification, a trainee is shown the assigned training activities which can be started by a simple click. In this **Passerelle Teach** workflow, instructors can follow along remotely and give live assistance via bidirectional audio and video streams. These streams and learning data are collected and stored for later review.

Passerelle XR also provides basic device management and app store & update services for XR headsets.

Whereas Explore and Teach are about “off-the-job” L&D experiences in virtual worlds, **Passerelle Guide** can enrich the real world with extra digital information, “on-the-job”, using mixed-reality devices (typically Microsoft HoloLens). Digital instructions, inspection procedures and more can be created in the no-code **Passerelle Author**. This provides an accessible solution to provide innovative and efficient learning and support in the real workplace. If MR headsets are not possible, we support Guide on tablets as well.

Finally we also offer Passerelle Coach, an XR solution for remote assistance by an expert from wherever in the world. The expert can see what you see, can assist with vocal help, directions, technical documents, AR annotations etc appearing in the field-of-view of the receiver.

3.1.1 Passerelle portal

The portal has several goals. It provides the core functionalities to streamline the use of XR content, plan and assign XR activities, collect learning data and support real-time assistance during XR sessions.

The backend of the portal also provides integration options to other learning platforms (e.g. Moodle or other LMS's).

Some important features:

- User management : define the use-case-specific roles and their permissions (e.g. trainer, trainee, coordinator, administrator, content designer, ...)
- Training management : Define training content, plan activities, monitor and assist in real-time, evaluate recorded training sessions
- Course / app management : Define courses (a.k.a. learning paths) linked to the VR apps available in the embedded app store.
- Device management : manage registered headsets and their security policies, training mode, app updates.
- Data repository : storage for XR assets, 3D models and also storage and passthrough for learning data captured in XR, forwarding selected data to external LMS's and/or Learning Record Stores (LRS's).
- Security : secured cloud storage with role-based access rights. Optional integration with available authentication / identity provider systems to reach a Single Sign On approach.

3.1.2 VR Lobby a.k.a. virtual workplace

This is the gateway to your XR experiences, where all participants have to pass. It provides an experience space that can be configured with specific 3D environments, media, explorations and interactions.

The main feature is to enforce the desired access control before allowing the trainee to see and launch the assigned training content.

Main features:

- Show VR activities as assigned in Passerelle Portal
- Check headset status and guide the user along the update flow
- Load and visualize customer-specific Lobby environment, media & 3D objects
- Provide multi-player explorations of workplaces, products etc

3.1.3 Passerelle author

Passerelle Author exists in 3 variations:

- A rich desktop editor to support the creation of XR training and support scenarios in manufacturing. This includes automated processing of CAD designs and transforming them into XR-ready assets and sample stepwise assembly or disassembly guidance procedures.
- An MR editor to easily create MR guidance steps on the workflow using an MR headset.
- A web-based editor as low-entry tool to prepare and maintain XR scenarios.

All authoring tools are interoperable thanks to a shared scenario modeling approach based on ISA-95 WorkDefinitions.

3.1.4 More info

Extensive user documentation for Passerelle XR can be found at: <https://xr-portal-documentation.supportsquare.io/latest/>

3.2 Ongoing work

In the scope of XR2INDUSTRY WP3, task T3.2 in particular, the consortium partners are still implementing remaining parts of the overall platform.

For Passerelle the following major topics are still ongoing:

- Migrating the MR editor from Microsoft HoloLens as authoring device to Android headsets such as Lynx.
- Finalizing the web-based Passerelle Author to support more advanced XR step configurations.
- Expanding XAPI data models to include ESCO classifications.

- Implementing support for designing and assigning digital learning credentials.
- Integrating Passerelle with T-Korp's Pulse MDM solution via the open MDM API's specified in XR2INDUSTRY.
- Integration with a federated content marketplace based on dataspace architecture, which is being implemented in XR2INDUSTRY.
- Implementing support for DID:web identification

4 Pulse – Unified XR device management & orchestration across any headset

4.1 Introduction

Pulse, developed by TKORP, is the XR2INDUSTRY platform's foundation for secure and scalable XR device management. Unlike traditional MDMs, Pulse is specifically designed for immersive XR deployments, enabling organizations to manage a heterogeneous fleet of XR headsets without being tied to a specific vendor.

Through its hardware-agnostic approach, Pulse supports Android-based XR devices from various manufacturers, including Pico, Meta, Lynx, HTC Vive, and more — giving organizations complete freedom in their hardware choices.

Pulse is composed of three main components:

- OpenMDM – the Express.js API backend for orchestration
- Pulse Web – the cloud-based management and content delivery portal
- Pulse Control – the offline companion app for local instructors and operators

4.2 Built for mixed XR fleets

Pulse enables seamless operations across diverse XR hardware with:

- Device provisioning using QR codes, enrollment tokens, or Android provisioning flows
- Application and content deployment regardless of the headset brand
- Policy enforcement: kiosk mode, app visibility restrictions, device lockdown
- Real-time orchestration, including launching apps and pushing training content
- Cloud and LAN-based delivery, ensuring reliability even in constrained networks
- Offline operations with Pulse Control, fully compatible with multi-vendor XR labs

4.3 Pulse web – cross-headset fleet control from the cloud

The Pulse Web portal provides centralized tools to manage any supported headset, across any site or brand:

- Monitor device health and connectivity
- Upload and assign apps, 360° content, and configuration profiles
- Launch synchronized training or demo sessions across different devices
- Interact with trainees via Pulse Control, whether online or offline
- Access unified logs and usage data across all brands
- Integrate with LMSs, analytics tools, or identity systems via the OpenMDM API

4.4 OpenMDM – an open, interoperable backend

OpenMDM offers a standardized API layer that abstracts away vendor-specific complexities, allowing:

- Seamless integration with LMSs, ERPs, or content platforms
- Uniform control over Pico, Meta, Lynx, HTC Vive, and other Android XR devices
- Centralized and secure content distribution with role-based access
- Authentication via Keycloak and support for DID:web identity schemes

This open, modular architecture makes Pulse ideal for environments using mixed hardware setups, without the need for device-specific code or infrastructure.

You can find the documentation here: <https://docs.pulse-xr.com/pulse-mdm>

4.5 Pulse control – local session management, vendor-agnostic

Pulse Control empowers trainers and operators to manage training sessions in offline or limited-connectivity environments, regardless of the XR headset in use:

- Discovers nearby devices over LAN using standard protocols (`_pulse._tcp.`)
- Launches apps and content directly on headsets from different vendors
- Provides simple, intuitive tools to trigger synchronized sessions
- Offers local diagnostics across various headset brands
- Ideal for labs, classrooms, or field deployments with heterogeneous XR fleets

4.6 Scalable, interoperable, vendor-neutral by design

Pulse ensures consistent control and orchestration capabilities across:

- Meta Quest
- Pico headsets (G2, Neo, 4K, etc.)
- Lynx R1
- HTC Vive XR Elite

- Any Android XR headset compliant with standard APIs

This cross-compatibility is native, not adapted — meaning organizations can evolve their hardware strategies over time without reengineering their software stack.

4.7 Ongoing Development in XR2INDUSTRY (T3.2)

As part of XR2INDUSTRY WP3 – Task T3.2, ongoing work includes:

- Adaptive live streaming across different headset capabilities
- Integration with the new Lynx Model with every architectures
- Dynamic quality adjustment based on real-world network conditions
- Integration with the federated XR content marketplace (via Eclipse Dataspace Connector)
- Support for credential issuance, xAPI extensions, and decentralized identities
- Interoperability with Passerelle and other XR2INDUSTRY tools

4.8 Conclusion

Pulse is the XR2INDUSTRY platform's operational backbone for device management, training orchestration, and content delivery — purpose-built for multi-vendor XR ecosystems. Whether you manage 10 or 10,000 headsets across brands, Pulse provides one unified interface, ensuring security, flexibility, and long-term sustainability.

5 Handle XR Application

5.1 Introduction

Altheria's Handle XR application enables users to create recordings of hand gestures and interactions with virtual objects using passthrough and hand tracking technology.

The functionality of the application can be grouped into 2 major parts depending on the type of user.

- **Editor:** A trainer can use the editor functions choose or import 3D objects and create new recording. Recordings are saved on the device.
- **Player:** A trainee can play a recorded sequence, allowing them to practice by patching the recorded movements with the help of real-time accuracy feedback and scoring.

The application is designed for XR training in Quality Assurance, primarily targeting the pharmaceutical and manufacturing sectors, though it is not limited to these industries.

The system addresses training needs where precise manual procedures and standardized interactions with objects are critical.

The application can be used fully standalone, or it can be integrated with web-based platforms such as Passerelle by Supportsquare or Altheria's platform to more easily manage your library of 3D assets, user data and screen casting the user's point of view over the internet.

5.2 Editor: record and edit trainings

The editor lets users create and modify their own training.

- Select a 3D asset included with the application or import 3D files from the web.
- If no 3D asset is selected, only the hand gestures are recorded. This lets the user create recordings on physical objects instead of virtual objects, which can be preferable in some cases. This also allows users to combine the XR application with their real environment, such as a laboratory or an assembly line.
- A video recording can be added to be displayed at the start of the training.

5.3 Player: practice on recorded trainings

In player mode, a user can select a sequence from the library to use for this training and receive a score based on how accurately they reproduce the gestures.

- Users can configure various parameters before the start of the training such as the playback speed, difficulty level, and left or right handedness.
- Users can view a video recording before or during the training.
- The user will see the hand outlines that were recorded by the instructor and which the user will have to match using their own hands. The outlines will change color.

5.4 Ongoing work

- ARuco code tracking: Physical Object tracking using printable CODE NAME that can be attached to physical objects.
- Integration with Eclipse Dataspace Connector to import 3D models.
- Integration with Supportsquare's Passerelle.
- Video recordings from the headset cameras.